

Modeling and control of double star induction machine by active disturbance rejection control

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ABSTRACT

This paper aims to contribute to the modeling and control of the double star induction machine (DSIM) by a robust method called active disturbance rejection control (ADRC). The ADRC has become in the last decade one of the most important techniques of regulation. This method is based on the use of an ESO (Extended State Observer) which estimates in real-time and at the same time the external disturbances and the errors due to the variations of the parameters of the machine and to the uncertainties of modeling. The two stators of DSIM are powered by three-phase inverters based on transistors and MLI control and the entire system is modeled in Park's reference. We analyze in the Matlab/Simulink environment the dynamic behavior of the system and the different ADRC controllers under different operating conditions. The result has demonstrated the performance and effectiveness of the ADRC.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The increase of the power of the electrical machines brings to light several problems as well at the level of the machine as of the inverter which provides its power. The static switches of the inverter must be sized to switch large currents which result in more power loss and accelerated aging of the electronic components of the inverter. The poly-phase machines offer a very interesting alternative to reducing stress on machine windings and converter switches [1].

These machines are usually composed of several stators allowing segmentation and reduction of power per phase. The use of the double star induction machine (DSIM) has increased considerably in recent years [2], especially in high-power applications such as rail traction, ship propulsion, electrical and hybrid vehicles, among others [2, 3]. The configuration of the DSIM is similar to a three-phase asynchronous cage machine with two stator windings offset in space by an angle generally equal to $\pi/6$. Each star winding is powered by a power electronics converter [4].

The double star induction machine has several advantages over the three-phase asynchronous machine such as the distribution of power over several phases, the possibility of torque reduction and improved reliability thanks to the ability to operate the DSIM with one or more phases in default [5, 6]. However, the DSIM still has some problems mainly related to the rate of harmonics in currents due to the presence of power converters, the non-linearity of its dynamic model and the complexity of its control [7].

The mathematical model of DSIM in the three-phase reference and Park's reference is similar to that of the three-phase induction machine, but with a higher number of magnitudes and equations. In this article we have chosen to use vector control with field-oriented control to operate the DSIM as an independent excitation DC machine, allowing for decoupling between electromagnetic torque and rotor flux [8]. The purpose of this decoupling is to control the speed of the machine and to maintain constant rotor flux.

The control of the double star induction machine is often by a PI regulator. This regulator has shown in reference [7] their performances and effectiveness in the control of DSIM. But it has some difficulty in parameter variations and load disturbance. The problem posed by the sensitivity lead the PI regulator to lose its performance. In this context, researchers are seeking to replace it with other regulation techniques to avoid sensitivity to the variation of machine parameters. Due to the limitation presented by the PI regulator and to improve the control of DSIM, we use a robust control strategy based on the control of DSIM rotor currents by ADRC (active disturbance rejection control) control loops.

The ADRC is a non-linear regulator that estimates and compensates in real-time the external disturbances and internal disturbances due to modeling uncertainties and machine parameter variations [9, 10]. This ADRC control strategy is based on an extended state observer known as ESO (Extended State Observer), which allows instantaneous estimation of all disturbances affecting the machine [9, 10]. This estimation is used in the generation of the control signal allowing the decoupling of the system from its disturbances [10].

The outline of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 is devoted to the modeling of DSIM. We develop also the principle and performance of the ADRC control strategy, then its implementation for the vector control of DSIM. In section 3, we present the results of the study of the dynamic behavior of the machine under different operating conditions. And a conclusion is taken in section 4.

2. RESEARCH METHOD

2.1. DSIM model

2.1.1. Representation of the DSIM

The DSIM studied in this article is squirrel-cage induction motor. Its stator is composed of two coils coupled in star and offset by an angle $\alpha = \pi/6$ [11]. Figure 1 illustrates the rotor and stator windings of the DSIM [12]. With θ_1 , θ_2 are respectively the angles between the rotor phase ra and the stator phases (sa_1) and (sa_2). α is the offset angle between the star windings (sa_1) and (sa_2).

Figure 1. DSIM windings

2.1.2. Park reference of DSIM model

Park's model consists of transforming a three-phase system (A, B, C) into a two-phase system (d, q), while maintaining power and the electromotive force. Figure 2 shows the rotor and stator windings of the DSIM in the Park reference [13]. Where θ_{s1} , θ_{s2} , θ_r are respectively the angles between the axis d and the stator phases (sa_1), (sa_2) and the rotor phase ra .

The equations of the voltages, in the two-phase reference (d, q) are expressed by the system of (1) [12-14]:

$$\begin{cases} V_{ds1} = R_{s1}i_{ds1} + \frac{d\psi_{ds1}}{dt} - \omega_s\psi_{qs1} \\ V_{ds2} = R_{s2}i_{ds2} + \frac{d\psi_{ds2}}{dt} - \omega_s\psi_{qs2} \\ V_{qs1} = R_{s1}i_{qs1} + \frac{d\psi_{qs1}}{dt} + \omega_s\psi_{ds1} \\ V_{qs2} = R_{s2}i_{qs2} + \frac{d\psi_{qs2}}{dt} + \omega_s\psi_{ds2} \\ 0 = R_r i_{dr} + \frac{d\psi_{dr}}{dt} - \omega_{gl}\psi_{qr} \\ 0 = R_r i_{qr} + \frac{d\psi_{qr}}{dt} + \omega_{gl}\psi_{dr} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

with $\omega_{gl} = \omega_s - \omega_r$.

The flux [12-14]:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_{ds1} = L_{s1}i_{ds1} + L_m(i_{ds1} + i_{ds2} + i_{dr}) \\ \psi_{ds2} = L_{s2}i_{ds2} + L_m(i_{ds1} + i_{ds2} + i_{dr}) \\ \psi_{qs1} = L_{s1}i_{qs1} + L_m(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2} + i_{qr}) \\ \psi_{qs2} = L_{s1}i_{qs2} + L_m(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2} + i_{qr}) \\ \psi_{dr} = L_r i_{dr} + L_m(i_{ds1} + i_{ds2} + i_{dr}) \\ \psi_{qr} = L_r i_{qr} + L_m(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2} + i_{qr}) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The expression of torque [14, 15]:

$$C_e = P \frac{L_m}{L_m + L_r} (\psi_{dr}(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2}) - \psi_{qr}(i_{ds1} + i_{ds2})) \quad (3)$$

Figure 2. DSIM model in Park's reference

2.2. Active disturbance rejection control strategy

The active disturbance rejection control was introduced by Han in 1995 [16]. It is a robust command based on the extension of the system model by a supplemental and fictitious state variable representing all the user cannot control in the mathematical model of the system controlled [17]. All real disturbances and modeling uncertainties are represented in this virtual state, the estimation of which is ensured by an extended state observer (ESO) [18-21]. Using this estimated state, a control signal is generated to decouple the system from the actual disturbance acting process. The ADRC application allows the user to treat the system as a simpler model because the negative effects of external disturbances and uncertainties of modeling are compensated in real time.

To illustrate the principle of the ADRC, we consider the following system first order [22, 23]:

$$y'(t) = f(t) + b_0U(t) \quad (4)$$

with, $U(t)$ and $y(t)$ are the input and output magnitudes of the system. $f(t)$ represents the sum of external disturbances, modeling errors and / or changes in system parameters. b_0 is a parameter known from the system under study. The state variable representation of the first-order system is described as follows [24]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_1 = x_2 + b_0 U \\ \dot{x}_2 = f \\ y = x_1 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

The basic idea of the ADRC is to implement an extended state observer (ESO) that provides an estimate $\hat{f}(t)$ such that the effect of $f(t)$ on the system can be compensated. The system control scheme is illustrated by the Figure 3 [25, 26]:

Figure 3. ADRC structure of a first order system

k_p is the gain of the proportional regulator which acts on $\hat{y}(t)$ rather than on the actual output $y(t)$. Its value is chosen according to the desired response time of the system studied in a closed loop. ESO is a Luenberger's observer that estimates the internal state variables of the system from the control input and the output.

The structure of this observer is expressed by the following model [24-27]:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{\hat{x}}(t) = (A - LC)\hat{x}(t) + Bu(t) + Ly(t) \\ \hat{y}(t) = C\hat{x}(t) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

with $A - LC = \begin{pmatrix} -\beta_1 & 1 \\ -\beta_2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$; $B = \begin{pmatrix} b_0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$; $L = \begin{pmatrix} \beta_1 \\ \beta_2 \end{pmatrix}$; $C = (1 \ 0)$

β_1, β_2 are the gains of the extended state observer and are generally determined by the pole placement technique. The rigorous determination of these gains makes it possible to guarantee to the observer a speed and sensitivity to the appropriate noises.

$$\beta_1 = 2 * \omega_0, \beta_2 = \omega_0^2$$

ω_0 and ω_c are respectively the ESO cut-off (break) pulse and the closed loop system cut-off pulse. The poles of the observer should be placed to the left of the pole of the closed loop to have faster dynamics.

$$\omega_0 = 3 \sim 10 \omega_c, \quad \omega_c = k_p$$

2.3. Implementation of ADRC in DSIM control

2.3.1. Vector control

To make the control of the electromagnetic torque of the DSIM independent from the rotor flux, we orient the latter in the direct axis of Park's reference and we keep it constant [28]:

$$\begin{cases} \psi_{dr} = \psi_r \\ \psi_{qr} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The electromagnetic torque is thus expressed by:

$$C_e = P \frac{L_m}{L_m + L_r} (\psi_r (i_{qs1} + i_{qs2})) \quad (8)$$

The flux expressions of (2) become:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \psi_{ds1} = (L_{s1} + e)i_{ds1} + ei_{ds2} + d\psi_r \\ \psi_{ds2} = ei_{ds1} + (L_{s1} + e)i_{ds2} + d\psi_r \\ \psi_{qs1} = (L_{s1} + e)i_{qs1} + ei_{qs2} \\ \psi_{qs2} = ei_{qs1} + (L_{s1} + e)i_{qs2} \\ i_{dr} = \frac{\psi_r - L_m(i_{ds1} + i_{ds2})}{L_r + L_m} \\ i_{qr} = \frac{-L_m(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2})}{L_r + L_m} \end{array} \right. \quad (9)$$

with e and d are constants:

$$e = \frac{L_m L_r}{L_r + L_m}, \quad d = \frac{L_m}{L_r + L_m}.$$

By replacing in (1), the expressions of rotor flux and currents given by (9), we express the direct and quadrature components of the stator voltages by:

$$V_{ds1} = R_{s1}i_{ds1} + L_{s1} \frac{di_{ds1}}{dt} - \omega_s((L_{s1} + e)i_{qs1} + ei_{qs2}) \quad (10)$$

$$V_{qs1} = R_{s1}i_{qs1} + L_{s1} \frac{di_{qs1}}{dt} + \omega_s((L_{s1} + e)i_{ds1} + ei_{ds2} + d\psi_r) \quad (11)$$

$$V_{ds2} = R_{s2}i_{ds2} + L_{s2} \frac{di_{ds2}}{dt} - \omega_s(ei_{qs1} + (L_{s2} + e)i_{qs2}) \quad (12)$$

$$V_{qs2} = R_{s1}i_{qs2} + L_{s2} \frac{di_{qs2}}{dt} + \omega_s(ei_{ds1} + (L_{s2} + e)i_{ds2} + d\psi_r) \quad (13)$$

for a decoupling between the quantities d and q , we put these expressions of tension in the form:

$$V_{ds1} = V_{d1} + e_{ds1} \quad (14)$$

$$V_{qs1} = V_{q1} + e_{qs1} \quad (15)$$

$$V_{ds2} = V_{d2} + e_{ds2} \quad (16)$$

$$V_{qs2} = V_{q2} + e_{qs2} \quad (17)$$

with:

$$e_{ds1} = -\omega_s((L_{s1} + e)i_{qs1} + ei_{qs2}) \quad (18)$$

$$e_{qs1} = \omega_s((L_{s1} + e)i_{ds1} + ei_{ds2} + d\psi_r) \quad (19)$$

$$e_{ds2} = -\omega_s(ei_{qs1} + (L_{s2} + e)i_{qs2}) \quad (20)$$

$$e_{qs2} = \omega_s(ei_{ds1} + (L_{s2} + e)i_{ds2} + d\psi_r) \quad (21)$$

and

$$V_{d1} = R_{s1}i_{ds1} + L_{s1} \frac{di_{ds1}}{dt} \quad (22)$$

$$V_{q1} = R_{s1}i_{qs1} + L_{s1} \frac{di_{qs1}}{dt} \quad (23)$$

$$V_{d2} = R_{s2}i_{ds2} + L_{s2} \frac{di_{ds2}}{dt} \quad (24)$$

$$V_{q2} = R_{s1}i_{qs2} + L_{s2} \frac{di_{qs2}}{dt} \quad (25)$$

Figure 4 shows the direct field-oriented control (DFOC) used for the control of the DSIM. This method is based on the estimation of the rotor flux module (ψ_r) and the phase(θ_s).

Figure 4. Direct field-oriented control of the DSIM

- Estimation of ψ_r

From the systems of (1) and (2) we deduce:

$$\frac{d\psi_r}{dt} = \frac{R_r L_m}{L_r + L_m} (i_{ds1} + i_{ds2}) - \frac{R_r}{L_r + L_m} \psi_r \quad (26)$$

hence the expressions of the rotor flux:

$$\psi_r = \frac{L_m}{1 + Tr.s} (i_{ds1} + i_{ds2}) \quad (27)$$

with $Tr = \frac{L_r + L_m}{R_r}$

- Estimation de θ_s

$$\theta_s = \int \omega_s dt \quad (28)$$

where $\omega_s = \omega_{gl} + \omega_r$

The expression of ω_{gl} is obtained from (1) and (2):

$$\omega_{gl} = \frac{R_r L_m}{L_r + L_m} \frac{(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2})}{\psi_r} \quad (29)$$

$$\theta_s = \int \left(\omega_r + \frac{R_r L_m}{L_r + L_m} \frac{(i_{qs1} + i_{qs2})}{\psi_r} \right) dt \quad (30)$$

2.3.2. Synthesis of the ADRC regulators

The strategy consists of controlling the stator currents of the DSIM by ADRC regulators. From (22-25), the stator currents of the DSIM can be expressed by:

$$\frac{di_{ds1,2}}{dt} = -\frac{R_{s1}}{L_s} i_{ds1,2} + \frac{1}{L_s} V_{d1,2} \quad (31)$$

and

$$\frac{di_{qs1,2}}{dt} = -\frac{R_{s1}}{L_s} i_{qs1,2} + \frac{1}{L_s} V_{q1,2} \quad (32)$$

We put these expressions in the following form:

$$\frac{di_{ds1,2}}{dt} = f_{d1,2}(t) + b_{0d1,2}U_{d1,2}(t) \tag{33}$$

and

$$\frac{di_{qs1,2}}{dt} = f_{q1,2}(t) + b_{0q1,2}U_{q1,2}(t) \tag{34}$$

with: $f_{d1,2}(t) = -\frac{R_s}{L_s}i_{ds1,2} + (\frac{1}{L_s} - b_{0d1,2})V_{d1,2}$; $U_{d1,2}(t) = V_{d1,2}$; $b_{0d1,2} = \frac{1}{L_s}$

and: $f_{q1,2}(t) = -\frac{R_s}{L_s}i_{qs1,2} + (\frac{1}{L_s} - b_{0q1,2})V_{q1,2}$; $U_{q1,2}(t) = V_{q1,2}$; $b_{0q1,2} = \frac{1}{L_s}$

$f_{d1,2}(t)$ and $f_{q1,2}(t)$ represent the total disturbances respectively affecting the currents isd_1 , isd_2 , isq_1 and isq_2 . $U_{d1,2}(t)$ and $U_{q1,2}(t)$ are respectively the control inputs of the current control loops isd_1 , isd_2 , isq_1 and isq_2 . $b_{0d1,2}$ and $b_{0q1,2}$ are the known parts of the system parameters. By choosing a suitable response time, we easily determine the parameters k_p , β_1 and β_2 of the ADRC regulators so that the stator currents follow perfectly their references as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Direct method (DFOC)

3. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

In order to verify the performance and the robustness of the active disturbance rejection control applied to the DSIM, the machine model and its vector control using the ADRC regulators are simulated in the Matlab/Simulink environment. The DSIM studied in this paper is fed by two voltage inverters at two levels, its electrical and mechanical parameters with the regulators gain are given in the appendix. In this section, three tests are simulated. The first test is devoted to illustrating the response of the machine in the load variation test. In the second test, we invert the speed direction. The third test is the robustness test.

3.1. Load variation test

The DSIM runs empty until time $t = 2$ s, when we introduce a load torque of 16 N.m, at $t = 4$ s we change the load torque from 16 N.m to 10 N.m. We note from Figure 6 that the speed of the DSIM follows its reference even after the load variation from 0 to 16 and from 16 to 10. Almost no overtaking or disturbance can move the speed away from its reference.

We also find that the electromagnetic torque varies proportionally to the stator currents in quadrature isq_1 and isq_2 , and it is independent of the rotor flux which is kept constant. The currents of each stator winding of the DSIM are perfectly sinusoidal and their amplitudes depend on the load conditions. The control strategy implemented based on ADRC regulators perfectly achieves a decoupling between the electromagnetic torque of the DSIM and the rotor flux.

Figure 6. Operation of the DSIM controlled by ADRC regulators with load variation

3.2. Speed inversion test

This test consists to simulate the ADRC command with changing speed reference at 4s and by applying a load of 16 N.m at $t = 2$ s. Figure 7 illustrates the evolution of electrical quantities and mechanics of the DSIM under these operating conditions. The rotation speed ω_r changes direction at $t = 4$ s and goes from 100 rad/s to -100 rad/s after a transient regime about 0.35 s.

This inversion of speed direction is accompanied by a change in the order of the phases of the stator currents, a disturbance of the electromagnetic torque and the current $isq1$ for a short time before they return to their initial reference values. The rotor flux is maintained constant and independent of the variation of the torque. The estimation and the compensation of the external disturbances, due to the variation of the load and the change of reference speed, by the ADRC regulators allowed the system to have very satisfactory performance.

Figure 7. Operation of the DSIM with inversion speed

3.3. Robustness test

The robustness test consists of varying the rotor resistor R_r , the moment of inertia J and the stator inductances of the DSIM. Indeed, the regulators' calculations are based on functions whose parameters are assumed to be fixed. However, in a real system, these parameters are subject to variations driven by different physical phenomena.

Figure 8 shows the evolution of the stator currents, the speed of rotation and the electromagnetic torque of the DSIM during a variation of 100% of the value of the rotor resistance R_r , the moment of inertia J and the stator inductances at time of 3 s. The variations of these parameters have almost no influence on the machine's operation because the ADRC controllers make it possible to automatically compensate for the disturbances due to these variations. The tracking of the reference is still ensured and the stability of the system is not affected by these parameter variations.

Figure 8. Operation of the DSIM with rotor resistor variation, the moment of inertia variation and the stator inductances variations ($R_r = 2 \cdot R_{rn}$, $J = 2 \cdot J_n$ and $L_{s1,2} = 2 \cdot L_{s1,2}$) at $t=3$ s

4. CONCLUSION

This paper is dedicated to present control of DSIM using the ADRC command. The model of the double star induction machine in the Park reference system has been developed and the ADRC theories are also presented. This command allows the compensation of all external disturbances, modeling errors and parametric variations of the system. These disturbances represent the main concern in electrical drive systems. We have seen through the results obtained in this article, that the control by the active disturbance rejection control ADRC offers very good performances and robustness because it allows having a stable operation by eliminating the effect of the disturbances due mainly to the variation of the machine parameters, the variation of the load conditions and the change of the speed of rotation. The control by ADRC can be a very interesting solution for the systems using double star induction machine such as electrical vehicles, rail traction, marine electric propulsion and wind generators to name but few.

APPENDIX

Parameters of the DSIM:

Rated power 4.5 KW

Number of pole pairs $P = 2$

Stator and rotor resistors:

$R_{S1} = R_{S2} = 0.86\Omega$, $R_r = 0.36\Omega$.

Stator and rotor inductances:

$L_{S1} = L_{S2} = 0.184H$, $L_r = 0.0246H$.

Mutual inductance: $L_m = 0.0537H$

Moment of inertia: $J = 0.025 \text{ kg.m}^2$

Coefficient of friction: $K_f = 0.001 \text{ Nms/rad}$

Parameters of the ADRC regulators of the stator currents: $K_p = 379.1709$, $b_0 = 5.4348$, $\beta_1 = 7.5834e+03$, $\beta_2 = 1.4377e+07$.

Parameters of the PI regulators of the rotor flux: $K_{p\psi_r} = 37.7358$, $K_{i\psi_r} = 175.0632$.

Parameters of the PI regulators of speed: $K_{p\omega_r} = 1.1865$, $K_{i\omega_r} = 11.8850$.

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